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Implementation of National Rural Health Mission in Kolhapur

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Abstract:

Health is one of the most important aspect that helps to develop capabilities and sustainability to work long and contributes towards economic growth. Health planning in India has come a long way since independence. During this period different sets of policies on health services have been proposed and implemented. The national health policy of 2002 stated that the situation was far from satisfactory. It was necessary to make provision for increased access to a decentralized public health system as well as to enhance public health investment within communicable disease programs. In this background the national rural health mission was launched.

For the progress of any country the people of the respective country should be healthy. With due consideration of this aim the central government of India has started the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) program on 12 April 2005. National Rural Health Mission Program basically started to improve the health facilities. On the other hand, the rural population has been facing less availability of health facilities. Initially this program was designed for a 7 year-period only (2005-2012). But thanks to the positive outcomes of this program the period has been extended. Indian Public Health Standard is a standard system created by the central government and the purpose behind it is that the primary health center,

sub-center and rural hospital in our country have some standards for making the health system quality, equipment, manpower, maintenance and cleanliness that will be strengthened. The main objective of this campaign is to decentralize the health services provided through this scheme and hand over all related powers to the Panchayat Samiti and Zilla Parishad and through them the planning and management of health services should be done properly.

Keywords: National Rural Health Mission and Implementation of National Rural Health Mission.

Introduction :-

Indian Public Health Standard is a standard system created by the central government and the purpose behind it is that the primary health center, sub-center and rural hospital in our country have some standards for making the health system quality, equipment, manpower, maintenance and cleanliness will be strengthened. Through this campaign, different schemes are implemented to increase the participation of the society in these health related programs. For that, they have been given the necessary funds and authority. At the village level, Asha, a health worker, has been appointed and with the help of the Gram Panchayat and Anganwadi, various service activities are being implemented for the good health of mothers and children.” Chauhan Gopal has studied and evaluated the key health Indicators of Himachal Pradesh in his study and this study shows that the health facilities provided through this scheme have a positive impact on the health of people. (Chauhan.G.2021p-35-41)

The Government of India launched the National Rural Health Mission in 2005 to provide health facilities to the under privileged and the poor. As a part of this, a health campaign has been established in Kolhapur district. According to this campaign, by coordinating the related programs and other health related programs with the participation of

private medical professionals and charitable organizations, the main objective of this campaign is to effectively implement the health related programs under this campaign. Different schemes are implemented in the district under this aim. Indian Public Health Standard is a standard system created by the central government and the purpose behind it is that the primary health center, sub-center and rural hospital in our country have some standards for making the health system quality, equipment, manpower, maintenance and cleanliness will be strengthened. Through this campaign, different schemes are implemented to increase the participation of the society in these health related programs. For that, they have been given the necessary funds and authority. At the village level, Asha, a health worker, has been appointed and with the help of the Gram Panchayat and Anganwadi, various service activities are being implemented for the good health of mothers and children.” Chauhan Gopal has studied and evaluated the key health Indicators of Himachal Pradesh in his study and this study shows that the health facilities provided through this scheme have a positive impact on the health of people. (Chauhan.G.2021p-35-41)

In Kolhapur district, since the National Health Mission started in all tehsils, there is an improvement in the health condition and there is also a decrease in the maternal mortality rate and infant mortality rate in the district, but there is still a need to reduce this rate and to increase the rate of institutional delivery. There is still a need to clear the doubts in the minds of the people about the government health facilities. It is necessary to create health awareness among them by giving them information about health facilities. “According to Desai Pratibha, Asha factors were appointed to bring health Facilities to the homes through which health facilities are provided to the people and awareness among the people.”(Desai.P.2016, p-11)

Objective of the study :-

- 1 . To study the concept of National Rural Health Mission (NRHM).
- 2 . To examine the implementation of National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) in Kolhapur district with special reference to Karveer and Hatkanangale tahsils

Hypotheses of Research Study :-

The hypotheses of the present research study are as follows

1. Implementation of National Rural Health Mission is significantly effective in Kolhapur District.

Research Methodology :-

The present research work is empirical and analytical types of research since it has covered grass root level scenario of the National Rural Health Mission in Karveer and Hatkanangale Tehsils and its outcome. Thus, the study is explorative in nature. The study was based on the following research methodology.

It has been identified that there are certain indices and parameters which are truly represent. The socio-economic impact of National Rural Health Mission is observed on beneficiary's life. In that sense it is also called as an analytical research. Thus, Present research work is empirical as well as analytical in nature.

Data Collection :-

In order to study the working of National Rural Health Mission in study region problem faced by the beneficiaries, perspectives and opinions of beneficiaries and its socio-economic

impact on downtrodden as well as vulnerable section of the society, researcher has used primary data to analyze the present study. The necessary secondary data has been collected from the different government reports and documents relating to the health services, published research works, articles, journals, newspapers and books

The concept of National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) :-

Introduction :-

In April 2005, Indian Government launched the National Rural Health Mission, which provides affordable and quality health care services in rural areas. With the provision of infrastructure facilities and funds, it also aims at strengthening rural health care institutions. Though there is improvement in flow of funds to rural health institutions and better health awareness, still defects like lack of surveys, good financial management, required infrastructure, human resources and timely up-gradation of health units have been noticed.

Working of NRHM :-

NRHM foresee an important role for communities in the delivery and monitoring of primary healthcare. One of the NRHM's core strategies is to build the capacity of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) to control and manage public health services. NRHM has a facility for professional bodies and non- governmental organizations to conduct monitoring and evaluation. It also depends on communities to observe the delivery system and the facility of health services. At the national level, NRHM is a joint Mission Steering Group, the Union Minister of Health and Family Welfare is heading this group. And an Empowered Programme Committee, headed by the Union Secretary for Health and Family Welfare. At the state level, the Chief Minister is heading the State Health Mission, and carries out the activities through State Health Societies. The District Health Mission, at the sub-state level is headed by Chairman of the Zilla Parishad and is assembled by the District Head of the Health Department.

All the relevant Departments, NGOs and private professionals should have representation in NRHM. For the entire period (2005-12), district Health Societies are responsible for preparing perspective plans, annual plans of all components and for integrating public health plans with those for water, sanitation, hygiene and nutrition. Block level health plans on the basis of district plans are formulated to integrate the village plans. Rogi Kalyan Samitis (RKS) at the block level are responsible for the day-to-day management of hospitals.

At village level, a Village Health and Sanitation Samiti is responsible to the Panchayat and consists of a female Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) and is the bridge for the village, an ANM, a teacher, a panchayat representative, and community health volunteers. Primary Health Centres consist of a medical officer and fourteen paramedical staff, and provide integrated medicinal and inhibitory care. At the block level, CHCs, serving as referral units for four PHCs, are manned by four medical 149 specialists (surgeon, physician, gynaecologist and paediatrician) and provide obstetric care and specialist consultations. NRHM seeks to bring CHCs and PHCs on par with Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS) and try to provide adequate funds and powers for improvement in facilities.

Problems In Implementation of NRHM :-

The major problem of NRHM is bad coordination and integration with other health institutions. The goals of NRHM is to enlarge expenditure on public health and to provide access to healthcare to the rural poor. It identifies that diseases are caused by a number of factors and focuses on the convergence of inter – sectorial services such as nutrition, water, sanitation and hygiene. It combines previously vertical disease-specific programmes at the national, state and district levels, ensuring that these different aspects are represented in the district health plan. NRHM is planned to coordinate endurance between related schemes such as Total Sanitation Services, Mid Campaign, Day Meal, Integrated and Child National

Development Disease Control Programmes for Malaria, TB, Kala Azar, Filariasis, Blindness & Iodine Deficiency and Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme. However, communication between different ministries and incorporation between various intersecting programmes is still there as the biggest challenge for NRHM. The NRHM structure states targets for public health outcomes, but not up to speed in mechanisms to evaluate state performance against goals. The Ministry of Health & Family Welfare keeps annual state-wise data, but without state targets in the framework, it is impossible to come at significant regional and inter-state comparisons.

Hypothesis Testing -

H₀: Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district.

H₁: Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district.

The effectiveness of the NRHM program implementation has been understood by taking into account the influence of different programs implemented under NRHM program. Janani Suraksha Yojana, Janani Shishu Suraksha Programs, Ayushman, Antenatal Care Program, General Facilities, Antenatal Care, Postnatal Care and Immunizations, Delivery by Trained Person, Free Quality Food, Free Treatment and Examination, Family Planning Surgery, Treatment of Communicable and Non-Communicable Diseases are major implemented programs under NRHM. Different facilities such as health facilities, vaccination program, service of Asha, benefits of JSY Yojana, benefits of JSSK Yojana, nutrition and hygiene programs, drug supply, prenatal facility, postpartum facilities, newborn care program, family planning program and breastfeeding mother diet.

Hypothesis Testing (Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test)

Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	Observed Median	Sig Value	Result
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Health Facility)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Health Facility)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Vaccination Program)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Vaccination Program)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Service of Asha)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Service of Asha)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis

Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	Observed Median	Sig Value	Result
Kolhapur district (Benefits of JSY yojana)	(Benefits of JSY yojana)			
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Benefits of JSSK yojana)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Benefits of JSSK yojana)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Nutrition and hygiene programs)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Nutrition and hygiene programs)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Drug Supply)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Drug Supply)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not	Implementation of NRHM is	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis

Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	Observed Median	Sig Value	Result
significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Prenatal Facility)	significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Prenatal Facility)			
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Postpartum facilities)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Postpartum facilities)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (New born care program)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (New born care program)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Family planning program)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Family planning program)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis

Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	Observed Median	Sig Value	Result
Implementation of NRHM is not significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Breastfeeding mother Diet)	Implementation of NRHM is significantly effective in Kolhapur district (Breastfeeding mother Diet)	4	.000	Failed to accept Null hypothesis

The table above shows the Wilcoxon's sign ranked test for the hypothesis compromising of different variables regarding effectiveness of NHRM program in Kolhapur district against test average person respondents of below 3 (below median score). From table, median-values for are health facilities (4), vaccination program (4), service of Asha (4), benefits of jsy yojana (4), benefits of jssk yojana (4), nutrition and hygiene programs (4), drug supply (4), prenatal facility (4), postpartum facilities (4), new born care program (4), family planning program (4) and breastfeeding mother diet (4). This shows that implementation of NHRM in Kolhapur district were significantly effective. The significance value is less than 0.05 which indicate the data is significant at 5% level. Hence, null hypothesis has been rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted with respect to the median value. Here Likert scale is used for measurement which ranges from 1 to 5, where 5 denotes excellent, 4 denotes very good, 3 is for good, 2 denotes fair, and 1 denotes poor. The sig. values of variables under study are less than 0.05.

Conclusion :-

The present study finds out the effectiveness of the NRHM program implementation through influence level of different programs implemented under NRHM program. Researcher followed Wilcoxon's sign ranked test for the hypothesis compromising of different variables regarding effectiveness of NHRM program in Kolhapur district against test average person respondents of below 3 (below median score). Median-values for are health facilities (4), vaccination program (4), service of Asha (4), benefits of jsk yojana (4), benefits of jssk yojana (4), nutrition and hygiene programs (4), drug supply (4), prenatal facility (4), postpartum facilities (4), new born care program (4), family planning program (4) and breastfeeding mother diet (4). It was observed that implementation of NHRM in Kolhapur district was significantly effective. The significance value is less than 0.05 which indicate the data is significant at 5% level. Hence, null hypothesis has been rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted with respect to the median value. It is seen here that national rural health mission in Kolhapur district has been implemented properly and effectively whichh has helped beneficiaries by providing said facilities.

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